

1 FEDERATED LEARNING FOR MULTICENTER COLLABORATIONS OF
2 SMALL BIOMEDICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS: A FRAMEWORK FOR
3 NAVIGATING CHALLENGES AND REALIZING OPPORTUNITIES
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26

27 **ABSTRACT**

28 The promises of Machine Learning (ML)-aided medicine have yet to be realized, in large part because robust optimization and
29 generalizability of ML models requires large training datasets, which are logistically challenging to obtain. The majority of ML
30 medical research is conducted using small- to mid-scale single institution datasets and does not equitably represent the general
31 population. For institutions with smaller footprint, resources, and catchment areas, the problem is exacerbated, making engagement
32 in high-quality ML model development challenging. The emergence of Federated Learning (FL) as a new discipline has great
33 potential to empower smaller institutions to collaboratively train algorithms for healthcare applications without sharing private
34 patient data. This will open the door for application of ML-assisted medicine in rural settings and other underrepresented contexts,
35 including for conditions with low prevalence. However, there remain numerous pragmatic concerns of how multicenter
36 collaborations can be coordinated between small, similarly resourced groups outside of joining large consortiums that are
37 coordinated around centralized, well-resourced leadership. We seek to address this problem by discussing the challenges faced by
38 federated coalitions of smaller biomedical research institutions and proposing a three-stage plan to facilitate (1) the formation of
39 an inter-institutional *Working Group*, (2) the design and engineering of operating policies and infrastructure, and (3) the execution
40 of study and open dissemination of lessons learned.

41

42 1. INTRODUCTION

43 Machine Learning (ML) and, in particular, Deep Learning (DL) have received significant attention in the popular press as emerging
44 fields with the opportunity to significantly alter the way we approach myriad problems. Healthcare is one domain that stands out
45 as having a lot to gain from ML/DL models; for example, a 2017 survey conducted on behalf of The Royal Society found that ML-
46 aided diagnosis was the type of application that the general public rated as having the highest ratio of potential social value to
47 potential social risk¹. However, despite the many potential benefits that ML/DL could offer healthcare professionals, biomedical
48 researchers, and patients alike, the adoption of these techniques for clinical use has been slow and limited in scope. Data access,
49 heterogeneity, stakeholder alignment, and privacy are among the primary obstacles that have prevented wide-scale use of ML/DL
50 systems for healthcare applications^{2,3}. The variation in clinical practices, data acquisition technologies, and patient demographics
51 from one institution to the next reduces the generalizability of models trained by any one institution on their respective dataset,
52 leaving already-underserved groups such as rural populations unable to benefit from state-of-the-art advances in ML^{4,5}. For
53 example, it has been estimated that half of DL models for diagnostic imaging were trained on existing NIH consortia and over two
54 thirds were trained on datasets from California, Massachusetts or New York⁶. Geographic generalizability is only one piece of the
55 puzzle — demographic, temporal, and contextual generalizability also need to be taken into account and further demonstrate the
56 inadequacy of existing datasets to meet the needs of clinicians and patients⁷. Academic institutions and medical systems with lower
57 catchment populations face significant obstacles in providing their investigators with access to large training datasets, but low
58 physician-to-patient ratios, long wait or drive times to see specialists, and differing prevalence of diseases in these populations
59 make them strong candidates for ML-aided medicine if sufficient data were available⁸.

60

61 Training ML/DL algorithms to be robust and deployable for personalized medicine requires a massive amount of data that is often
62 incredibly costly to generate and ends up isolated from the rest of the world in the data silo of the research institution or health
63 system that owns it⁹. As a result, small research institutions are at a severe disadvantage and may become dependent on centralized
64 public datasets that suffer from generalizability issues and can leave them vulnerable; for example, tissue and diagnostic slide
65 images hosted by The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) — a cancer genomics program and database run by the National Cancer
66 Institute — were offline from late spring until mid-fall of 2021, leaving research groups without their own datasets few options for
67 model development¹⁰. Gaining access to repositories containing data relevant to common diseases and demographics can be
68 challenging enough, but even major research institutions may not have enough data to develop ML/DL algorithms concerned with
69 rarer conditions and sub-populations on their own¹¹. The scarcity of data for developing pediatric oncology models provides a
70 poignant example of one such context in which collaboration is required to improve patient outcomes¹²⁻¹⁴. Individual hospitals or
71 universities may lack sufficient data to train models independently, but pooling data can expose already vulnerable groups to risk
72 of privacy violations, requires robust storage and data harmonization infrastructure and may only be as complete as the participating
73 institutions allow. While public sharing of hospital data promises to be a democratizing force by fostering collaboration while
74 providing data access to many, there exists unresolved legal, ethical, and logistical concerns limiting the sharing of medical data
75 between research institutions. Federated Learning (FL) offers a way forward by facilitating collaborative training on distributed
76 datasets without requiring that participating data-owners provide access to anyone else. This is accomplished by training separate
77 models on each private dataset and iteratively sharing the model parameters across institutions to produce an aggregate model that
78 benefits from the collective data of all participants, as depicted in Figure 1A (see the Background section “Overview of Federated
79 Learning”).

80 While significant research has focused on the theoretical and technical considerations underlying aggregation algorithms,
81 communication efficiency, and security and privacy of training data and the resulting models in FL environments¹⁵, there is a
82 paucity of literature devoted to navigating the logistical and pragmatic roadblocks for groups seeking to coordinate multicenter
83 studies on private health data through a federated system. This issue has been particularly understudied amongst smaller research
84 institutions. While efforts to develop large, federated consortiums exist, these efforts are typically led by institution with sufficient
85 resources and funding^{9,16-19}. Smaller research institutions and catchment regions (e.g., rural locale) that are disproportionately
86 underfunded may lack sufficient infrastructure for either taking on leadership roles or partaking equitably in such collaborations.
87 Such challenges may disadvantage these smaller institutions, potentially leading to underrepresentation of important patient
88 demographics. We aim to address this knowledge gap by enumerating the intra- and inter-institutional hurdles that must be
89 overcome for a successful FL collaboration and by articulating a potential framework for the formation of a multi-institutional
90 *Working Group*.

91 We will begin with a brief overview of FL (section 2.1) and its benefits (section 2.2) and drawbacks (section 2.3), but our discussion
92 will focus on a call-to-action (section 3) for smaller research institutions to leverage FL as a tool for more effective collaboration
93 and a roadmap of questions such groups need to ask themselves in order to achieve this goal. As a preview of what is to come, our
94 plan broadly covers the: 1) preplanning (e.g., working group formation; section 3.2), 2) planning (e.g., funding, infrastructure;
95 section 3.3), and 3) execution/evaluation (e.g., implementation and dissemination, relationship maintenance; section 3.4) aspects
96 of setting up such a collaboration

97 2. BACKGROUND

98 2.1. OVERVIEW OF FEDERATED LEARNING

99 2.1.1. MACHINE LEARNING IN BIOMEDICINE

100 To understand Federated Learning, we need to begin with a shared vocabulary for Machine Learning and Deep Learning. Machine
101 Learning is a field that consists of a wide range of tools for classifying, forecasting, summarizing, clustering, or otherwise
102 transforming information from one data type into another that may be more useful for a given task. With this broad definition,
103 many techniques that may be more frequently expressed in the language of statistics, such as logistic regression or Principal
104 Components Analysis (PCA), can also be considered examples of ML algorithms. However, traditional statistical techniques may
105 struggle when the number of predictors far exceeds the number of observations, where predictors may be highly multicollinear and
106 may express unknown interactions with other predictors or exhibit a complex and unintuitive dependence with respect to the
107 outcome variable. Although rare outcomes, biased inference, fairness, reliability and limited interpretability/explainability are still
108 significant obstacles, recent advances in machine learning are better equipped to deal with the challenges posed by complex
109 dependency structures and interactions among predictors and have opened the door for many exciting applications in healthcare
110 and biological research. These include data mining algorithms to extract semantic relationships from clinical observations encoded
111 in text, classifying and segmenting medical images, leveraging -omics data to identify potential drug targets, and much more; for
112 a review of opportunities and challenges to Deep Learning in biomedicine, we refer the reader to²⁰. We provide a glossary table of
113 key terms for ML highlighting the topics covered here and in the following two subsections in the supplementary materials.

114 2.1.2. Neural Nets and Gradient Descent

115 One of the most influential ML methods that is not as familiar to classical statisticians is the Artificial Neural Net (ANN), named
116 after its loose resemblance to, and inspiration from, a network of neurons in the central nervous system. An ANN is composed of
117 nodes organized in layers that are connected sequentially and propagate information throughout the network. Each connection
118 between nodes is given a certain weight that multiplicatively transforms the incoming values, and an optional additive bias that can
119 transform the weighted value before it is passed through an activation function. The weights and biases of the net are collectively
120 referred to as the model parameters and define the function that is approximated by the network. Networks with many layers are
121 also called Deep Neural Nets (DNNs) and are the origin of the term Deep Learning^{20,21}. A Convolutional Neural Net (CNN) is one
122 type of DNN that has been particularly successful for biomedical imaging applications due to its ability to represent complex spatial
123 or temporal relationships within the data. The parameters in each layer of a CNN define a filter or kernel that is convolved over the
124 input such that the output of each layer contains information about the correlations across the input — for example, the filters of a
125 CNN successfully trained on image data will detect very low-level features, such as edges or curves, in early layers, and abstract
126 features, such as the parts of a cell, in later layers²¹. It has been demonstrated that a network with a sufficient number of layers can
127 theoretically approximate any continuous function within a small margin of error²²; this is accomplished by computing an error
128 metric between the model predictions and the ground truth that is known as the loss and updating the model parameters in the
129 direction that minimizes the loss. Backpropagation of error throughout the network is used to calculate the gradient of the loss
130 function with respect to each of the model parameters for any given input, but this is often done for only one randomly selected
131 input in a batch to increase the efficiency of the training process in a strategy called Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD). While
132 SGD can be an effective method for finding local minima in the loss function, there is no guarantee that the global minimum will
133 be found²¹. There are many optimizers that have been developed to improve on basic SGD and increase the likelihood of finding a
134 globally optimal model, but these are out of scope for our discussion here.

135

136 There are three broad domains from which ANNs are utilized in biomedicine: 1) images (e.g., X-rays, CT scans, pathology slides,
137 with applications in classification, segmentation, denoising, registration, real-time tracking)^{23–25}, 2) genetic/molecular data (e.g.,
138 gene expression, DNA Methylation, mutational panel; predicting disease survival, finding unknown associations with health and
139 disease outcomes) and 3) textual/electronic health record data (e.g., natural language processing on clinician notes, diagnostic
140 codes, procedures, curation of structured databases through named entity recognition, prospective prediction of patient outcomes)²⁶.
141 Several well cited examples of ANN in the biomedical literature include: 1) *MethylNet*, a modeling framework which can perform
142 unsupervised clustering, classification and regression tasks on DNA Methylation data²⁷, 2) *Alpha Fold*, an ANN that can predict
143 3D protein structure from amino acid sequences, accelerating drug discovery and design²⁸, and 3) *TOAD*, an ANN framework that
144 can predict the tumor site of origin from large gigapixel images of tissue slides taken from areas of metastasis²⁹.

145 2.1.3. DISTRIBUTED TRAINING

146 ANN models in an FL environment are trained in a distributed fashion, typically using Distributed SGD. In a Distributed SGD
147 environment, several models are trained via SGD in parallel and are updated by combining the gradients of each model, for example,
148 by taking the average gradient across models and using it to update all model parameters. The most popular form of Distributed
149 SGD in FL is FedAvg, in which each local model takes an SGD step on the starting model and the aggregation server then finds
150 the average gradient of the resulting models, weighted by the size of each local dataset³⁰. The local models are then updated with
151 the aggregated gradient prior to the next round of training. It is worth noting that the models can share gradients and update by
152 taking a step in the direction of the aggregate gradient or can share parameters and update by replacing the previous weights and

153 biases with the aggregated parameters; if the aggregation algorithm is a simple average, learning rates and initial parameters are
 154 consistent across local models, and all parameters or gradients are shared, these strategies are functionally equivalent. Figure 1
 155 shows a high-level overview of the iterative FL process; in practice, distributed training also requires that participants establish
 156 operating procedures, model architecture, experimental settings, and common ontologies for semantic harmonization of data before
 157 training can commence, but here we focus on describing FL as it differs from centralized ML approaches.

158

159 **FIGURE 1:** A.) An abstracted overview of the core steps for federated training: local training, sharing model parameters or
 160 gradients, aggregating the parameters or gradients, and updating local models with the new aggregate model. B.) These steps are
 161 repeated iteratively until a predefined stopping point or metric of model convergence or performance is reached. C.) After
 162 convergence, each institution may perform local fine-tuning before handing off the model to clinicians or advancing it to the next
 163 stage of validation.

164

165 As depicted in Figure 1A, the first step in model training is for each data-owner to train a model on their private data locally. The
 166 model parameters are then shared with an aggregation server in step 2 and used to produce the updated global model in step 3. The
 167 last step in each FL round is to update the local model parameters with the newly-aggregated parameters — after this, the process
 168 is repeated again from step 1 through step 4 with the updated local models and iterative refinement continues until the desired
 169 global model is reached. The stopping point could be a set number of training rounds, a metric of update size, a performance metric
 170 (e.g., accuracy on a central validation set or aggregated across each institution’s validation set), or any other criteria agreed upon
 171 by participants. There are, of course, a number of variations on this basic system, for instance: 1) hospital records may have different
 172 attributes for the same patients, 2) same attributes for different patients, 3) a subset of all available participants may be selected for
 173 training in any given round, 4) training may be carried out asynchronously if participant availability varies, 5) there may be multiple
 174 aggregation servers, 6) updates may be passed from one participant to the next in series rather than to an aggregation server in
 175 parallel, and 7) aggregation methods may be more nuanced (e.g., optimal ordering of image filters) than the basic FedAvg
 176 implementation^{15,31}. With that being said, the core concepts of FL remain the same for our purposes in all these cases and the
 177 system we have described above is sufficient to demonstrate the benefits of FL and challenges that prevent its widespread adoption.
 178 Some of these benefits and challenges are described in Table 1 below, and an expanded version is available in Supplementary Table
 179 1.

180

Benefits and Opportunities	Drawbacks and Challenges
Private data are never shared and access is revocable	Any application of ML-aided medicine can still be subject to bias and limited interpretability
Leverage existing policies and infrastructure for data storage, access, and use	Data heterogeneity can reduce performance
Decrease potential for algorithmic or systemic bias by using multiple datasets for differing contexts	Increasing the number of people and devices used for training leads to a larger attack surface
Improve generalizability and study rare diseases or populations	Model updates still leak some information
Distributed datasets and expertise are more robust than centralized	Computational and networking infrastructure must be available to all collaborating groups
Collaboration is well-motivated by the ethos of open science	Stakeholder alignment is hindered by the lack of general familiarity with FL
Enabling small institutions to become stakeholders in ML-aided medicine can expand access to its benefits	Data must be recorded and stored systematically to ensure semantic harmonization

181 TABLE 1: *A summary of the key benefits and challenges of FL for digital healthcare, focusing on the context of multicenter*
182 *collaborations among small research institutions.*

183 As depicted in Table 1, several of the pros and cons of FL in biomedical research pertain to the security and privacy of the training
184 data and the model. We provide an expanded discussion of privacy and security in ML and direct readers to additional resources
185 in the supplementary materials. For recent reviews of FL in biomedical research, we refer the reader to ^{3,9,32,33}.

186 2.2. BENEFITS OF FEDERATED LEARNING FOR SMALL RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS

187 2.2.1. PRIVATE DATA STAYS PRIVATE

188 The primary motivation for applying FL to tasks in digital healthcare is readily apparent from the definition of FL: models can
189 benefit from the information contained in a large collective dataset without requiring that the training data held by participants be
190 shared or centralized. Since only the model parameters are shared between institutions, the privacy integrity of each institution’s
191 dataset is maintained. This is particularly valuable in healthcare not only because data is subject to special legal and ethical
192 protections, but also because models developed for clinical applications have seen slow adoption due to the crisis in generalizability,
193 reproducibility, and reliability^{9,11,34}. For advances in ML to translate into better-informed clinical decision-making and improved
194 patient outcomes, the models developed for such purposes need to be trained on larger and more diverse datasets that better
195 represent the overall population we would like to benefit from these models^{6,7,9,11}. This presents an unprecedented opportunity for
196 collaborations of small-scale institutions to advance the state-of-the-art and help shape the future of algorithmically-informed
197 healthcare.

198 2.2.2. SMALLER INSTITUTIONS, GENERALIZABILITY, AND EQUITABILITY

199 Researchers continually find that observational studies in healthcare fail tests of reproducibility and that prediction models are
200 rarely subjected to the proper internal, internal-external, and external validation procedures that should be carried out to ensure
201 their reliability^{7,9,11,35}. Bias in public datasets has received significant attention recently following several reviews that found ML
202 models used for diagnosis and prognosis of Covid-19 from chest X-ray and computed tomography (CT) images were subject to
203 significant selection bias or potential for confounding, rendering these models dangerous³⁶⁻³⁸. Additionally, public datasets
204 insufficiently cover key target subpopulations for many tasks, especially in the context of disadvantaged/underserved groups.
205 Consider a recent analysis of multiethnic machine learning schemes in clinical omics, which found that out of 1600 potential
206 machine learning tasks derived from the TCGA database, only 447 could be carried out for both European Americans and African
207 Americans due to data inequalities³⁹. This shortcoming of existing data is exacerbated by limited generalizability of models across
208 demographic distributions, as demonstrated by the poor performance of skin lesion detection and classification models when
209 making predictions for dark-skinned patients⁴⁰.

210 Indeed, there are a range of challenges related to generalizability of models and bias in even the largest datasets that biomedical
211 researchers must overcome in order for the potential benefits of ML-aided healthcare to be realized. There is no question that data
212 sharing agreements among massive urban health systems or public NIH repositories have facilitated significant advances, but these
213 approaches have so far proved insufficient to address inequalities. FL can serve as an additional tool with great promise to support
214 equitable model development in a way that other approaches have not: by integrating the information we can extrapolate from the

215 highly diverse datasets of smaller institutions spread out across the nation and the world who serve underrepresented populations
216 in rural localities and with a wider range of care practices. Much work will need to be done in order to make this dream a reality,
217 but without FL it is difficult to imagine how these institutions could efficiently become stakeholders in model development.

218 2.2.3. STRENGTH IN DECENTRALIZATION

219 In addition to the core motivations articulated above, there are quite a few additional advantages in using FL to facilitate multicenter
220 collaborations among small institutions relative to the traditional approach of data sharing. While decentralized data sharing
221 networks such as the 4CE consortium or the TriNetX Analytics Network (Cambridge, MA), a global federated health research
222 network, have enabled rapid retrospective analysis of large cohorts, these types of collaborations can face restrictions when it comes
223 to patient-level analysis or investigations of rare sub-populations due to privacy concerns⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. By eschewing the need to pool data,
224 FL allows research groups to avoid the reduplication and transfer of large datasets. Existing storage infrastructure can be used as it
225 has been before, and intra-institutional policies for data access can be efficiently integrated into the broader data governance systems
226 of inter-institutional agreements^{9,11}. A fortunate side-effect of decentralized data storage is that the computational burden of model
227 training is distributed across participants in proportion to the size of their datasets, which is likely to scale with available computing
228 resources (i.e., larger institutions are more likely to have both bigger datasets and more computing power than smaller institutions).
229 Another benefit of FL is that maintaining a distributed dataset limits the vulnerability that centralized datasets are subject to, as any
230 one data-owner going offline is not overly detrimental to the success of the collective effort. For example, it is estimated that nearly
231 two thirds of ransomware attacks against healthcare organizations successfully encrypt data and the average total cost of
232 remediating an attack is 1.85 million USD⁴⁵. Consider the potential impact of a ransomware attack against a central repository
233 relative to an attack against one participant in an FL agreement — accounting for downtime and opportunity cost, it is easy to see
234 how detrimental and expensive such an incident would be if it impacts all institutions involved in the collaboration.

235 Centralized datasets also do not have guarantees for revocable access. If data were pooled and it was later revealed that some
236 individuals represented in the cohort could be identified by combining multiple attributes to find a unique record — a weakness of
237 anonymization strategies that has been repeatedly demonstrated — the damage has already been done. It would not be possible to
238 prove that none of the participants with access to the shared repository had made backups containing the sensitive records. In
239 contrast, a participant in a federated training system who fears improper deidentification of their data could simply stop sharing
240 model updates until the matter has been resolved internally and would know that no one outside their institution ever had access to
241 the data in question⁹. In some domains, such as genomic data, it may not even be possible to effectively anonymize the data without
242 removing potentially valuable information, since the total combination of a person's genes is nearly always uniquely identifying.
243 Finding the right balance between preserving patient privacy by maintaining the confidentiality of the data and maximizing the
244 information this data contains is still relevant to FL, however, and represents perhaps the greatest technical obstacle for widespread
245 implementation of FL in biomedical research^{3,9}.

246 2.3 CHALLENGES FOR FEDERATED EFFORTS

247 2.3.1. THE PRIVACY VS. UTILITY TRADEOFF

248 FL is not a panacea and there are still a number of challenges that must be addressed and overcome. One central theme that unites
249 many questions under the same umbrella is how to find a balance between privacy and utility in model development^{9,11,46-48}. At
250 one end of the spectrum is a centralized approach in which all training data are pooled; this is the gold-standard strategy to maximize
251 model performance, but it sacrifices data confidentiality^{11,34,48}. FL gives confidentiality a higher priority, but perfect patient privacy

252 cannot be guaranteed while still producing a useful model. Though training data is never directly shared, the model parameters
253 uploaded to the aggregation server necessarily contain abstracted information about the training data — if the parameters were not
254 capturing some features of the data, they could not be useful for the task at hand⁴⁹. There are a range of methods to limit information
255 leakage during training, such as using a differential privacy framework to add random noise to shared parameters, generating
256 synthetic data for model training, restricting the parameters that are shared to those that changed the most since the previous round,
257 or even sharing updates less frequently and iterating fewer times. However, any of these methods will come at a price: limiting the
258 information shared during training will intuitively limit the trained model’s ability to effectively distill information from the training
259 data, leading to worse performance^{49,50}. This is not an all-or-nothing issue, as many FL projects have successfully found a good
260 balance between privacy and utility, but it does mean that the specifics of an FL implementation can be highly context-dependent
261 and that researchers need to ask themselves how much patient privacy can justifiably be given up in exchange for a working model.
262 The consequences of attacks on privacy are steep — not only is patient trust violated, but researchers and institutions responsible
263 for maintaining data confidentiality could be subject to significant legal and financial repercussions.

264 2.3.2. MALICIOUS PARTICIPANTS

265 A closely-related challenge for FL efforts is that it requires a certain level of trust between the collaborating parties. The information
266 leakage discussed previously would not be as concerning if there was perfect trust between the collaborators and there were not
267 sophisticated attacks that can leverage information leakage to expose private data⁴⁹. Increasing the number of people and devices
268 involved in model training necessarily increases the attack surface; in a federated setting it is theoretically possible for any
269 collaborator to be an adversary. The literature on FL is expanding rapidly, with quite a bit of attention falling on the possible attacks
270 on privacy and security. Attacks on privacy include model inversion attacks in which the adversary produces samples that closely
271 mimic the most common features of the training data by generating examples that maximize the model’s confidence (e.g., what
272 features constitute a positive or negative case?), membership inference attacks in which the adversary’s goal is to determine whether
273 a given sample was in the training dataset of another participating institution, and attribute inference attacks in which the adversary
274 seeks to determine a missing attribute of a record given all other attributes^{46,47}. Attribute inference attacks are of special concern in
275 the context of healthcare, because public datasets used for training are commonly obfuscated to remove attributes that could be
276 uniquely-identifying and these attributes could be retrieved if the full records are used for training by one of the participants. It is
277 worth noting that in the context of healthcare data, reidentification of records is typically a more significant threat to privacy than
278 leakage of aggregate sub-population features. Attacks on security include data poisoning attacks and model poisoning attacks. As
279 the private data cannot be directly inspected for integrity without compromising confidentiality, it is possible for malicious
280 participants to poison their dataset by selectively manipulating labels or by inserting perturbations called backdoors that can be
281 used to trigger a desired response when they are added to arbitrary inputs. Often more dangerous than data poisoning attacks, model
282 poisoning attacks manipulate the model parameters or gradients directly to degrade performance broadly or only on specific
283 examples, depending on the attacker’s goal^{46,47}. While we would hope that a collaboration of research organizations to train models
284 for ML-aided healthcare would not include participants who seek to expose private data or reduce model accuracy, the larger attack
285 surface of a distributed environment warrants consideration, especially when the consequences of privacy infringements or poor
286 predictions are as high as they are in medical applications.

287 2.3.3. NON-IID AND HETEROGENEOUS DATA

288 Perhaps a more realistic problem for biomedical researchers using FL is data heterogeneity. As we have articulated previously, the
289 prospect of creating more generalizable models is one of the key motivations for utilizing FL in digital health — however, the use
290 of data from a wider distribution also poses challenges for model convergence. Differing institutions will likely have different

291 dataset sizes, prevalence of certain predictive variables or outcomes, and practices for encoding variables and representing
292 data^{2,3,32,51}. Many of the most popular aggregation algorithms for FL assume that data are independent and identically distributed
293 (IID), but this is often not the case in real-world use-cases for FL and the best practices for dealing with non-IID data are still a
294 topic for much research and debate¹⁵. Beyond the assumptions regarding independence and distributions of data, researchers
295 working with real datasets that have not been specially curated for FL may have differing conceptual mappings between medical
296 observations and data attributes. This challenge is not unique to FL, as collaborations built around centralized repositories will also
297 have to manage semantic harmonization of data, but it remains a significant task. The questions that need to be asked about this
298 can be highly context-specific: what staging system and criteria are used, are the methods and machinery for staining and digitizing
299 histology slides the same across hospitals (and even across samples from the same hospital), is blood pressure recorded when the
300 patient is sitting up or laying down, and so on. Standardized notations and data formats such as the Observational Medical Outcomes
301 Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) for Electronic Health Records (EHR) and related tools developed for the
302 Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) collaborative or similar efforts can be of use here, but are not
303 sufficient to address all of these issues^{52,53}. FL efforts must take further precautions to limit bias and understand the data generating
304 mechanism without compromising privacy in order to build useful models.

305 2.3.4. LOGISTICAL CHALLENGES

306 In addition to the considerations we have raised so far, there are a number of pragmatic problems that must be solved for federated
307 collaborations to succeed. One such issue that needs to be addressed early in any project is to determine what funding is needed
308 and how it can be procured. For example, will new computing infrastructure have to be purchased, will one institution sponsor the
309 project and train researchers at other institutions, can some researchers be subcontracted on an existing grant, are existing datasets
310 curated appropriately or will they require paid annotators, and so on. The networking components will also need to be engineered
311 such that institutions can send model updates to each other in a timely manner, which will require navigating firewalls or other
312 security protocols and working closely with information technology groups at each institution involved in training or aggregation.
313 These groups may also be consulted to determine how code execution environments can be cross-compatible with resources
314 available to each institution (see section 2d for more on this). Obtaining approval from Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) can be
315 an additional challenge and may be dependent on the IRBs' knowledge of and familiarity with FL; preliminary studies may require
316 the worst-case assumption that FL is as serious a threat to patient privacy as pooling data would be. These logistical challenges
317 pertaining to financing, communicating updates, and securing approval will be discussed in more detail throughout our proposal as
318 we describe avenues for overcoming obstacles and building successful partnerships.

319 2.3.5. SECURING BUY-IN

320 Beyond the theoretical and logistical concerns expressed above, a serious obstacle in the way of federated collaborations is the
321 difficulty in securing buy-in from multiple research groups. Fairness in the distribution of funding, ownership of algorithms, and
322 decisions regarding commercialization or publication (e.g., author order) are important considerations for any project to train
323 models cooperatively, including traditional multicenter studies that rely on data sharing agreements. For FL collaborations however,
324 these issues are exacerbated by the other challenges we have enumerated and by the fact that FL is still a fairly novel technique,
325 emerging as a distinct field of research only in 2016^{15,30}. Researchers may be reluctant to bring FL proposals before an IRB that
326 has not evaluated FL projects previously, given their familiarity with the involved process of obtaining approval for traditional
327 multisite studies and the prospect that this process may be more ambiguous without central leadership. Participation in a
328 collaborative FL study can be seen as a risk with unknown technical and pragmatic challenges without a clear way forward — our

329 primary goal in this work is to address this gap in understanding by describing these challenges as we have above and proposing a
330 roadmap for small groups to build federated collaborations below.

331 3. PROPOSAL

332 3.1. OVERVIEW

333 We propose a three step plan for small institutions to follow in order to build cooperative studies based on FL for digital healthcare
334 applications: (1) the *Preplanning Stage* in which the core unit of the collaboration — the *Working Group* — is formed and the
335 goals and challenges are established; (2) the *Planning Stage* guides the *Working Group* through the challenges that have been
336 identified in the previous step, breaking them down into issues pertaining to (a) financing, (b) data governance, (c) ethics, and (d)
337 computational infrastructure; and (3) the *Execution and Evaluation Stage* consisting of (a) the Dry Run, (b) finalization of the
338 experimental setup, (c) training and testing, (d) formalizing and sharing knowledge, and (e) maintaining relationships. We
339 emphasize that the challenges and opportunities that motivated this proposal arise from the context of smaller institutions and are
340 not necessarily applicable to larger teams. This conceptual framework is put forth as a generalizable hierarchical decomposition of
341 the checkpoints between initial conception of an FL project and achieving its goals, but the progression through these checkpoints
342 may not necessarily be linear and deterministic in all cases. Our proposal, summarized in Figure 2, is designed with this flexibility
343 in mind and additional discussion will be devoted to variations we anticipate where they are relevant. In the following sections we
344 will provide more detail on each of the three stages and reference the challenges introduced above as points for the *Working Group*
345 to investigate. The three step structure is inspired by a previous framework proposed for organizing a multicenter clinical trial⁵⁴.

346

347 FIGURE 2: Overview of the proposed framework. The Preplanning Stage focuses on the formation of a Working Group, which is
 348 further developed by establishing goals and maintaining relationships. The Assessment of Institutional Readiness provides dynamic
 349 tools for assessing accomplishments and challenges throughout the project's progression and serves to bridge the gap between
 350 Preplanning and Planning. The Planning Stage requires detailed procedures and policies be put into place for financing, data
 351 governance, ethical and institutional approvals, and engineering computational infrastructure for FL. When these have been
 352 sufficiently refined, the Dry Run is used to evaluate the inter-institutional readiness so the Execution and Evaluation Stage can
 353 proceed through the finalization of experimental settings and the actual training and testing of the FL model. Findings regarding
 354 not just the technology in question but also the cohesion and organization of the Working Group's project as a whole should be
 355 formalized and shared to enrich the literature on multicenter collaborations of this type. The Working Group may continue to
 356 iterate or extend their project, but even if it is ultimately disbanded after the project's goals are achieved, we advocate that
 357 relationships be maintained when looking forward to grow the network of small research institutions using FL for digital
 358 healthcare.

359

360 3.2. STEP 1: THE PREPLANNING STAGE

361 The first step in our proposed framework for multicenter FL, the *Preplanning Stage*, focuses on building relationships with potential
 362 collaborators and laying a scaffold to fill in as the project develops. The three components of this step are depicted in Figure 3.

363

364

365
 366 FIGURE 3: *The three components of the Preplanning Stage: Working Group Formation, Establishing Goals and Building*
 367 *Relationships, and the Assessment of Institutional Readiness.*

368 **3.2.1. WORKING GROUP FORMATION**

369 The primary goal of the *Preplanning Stage* is the successful creation of a collective of personnel across institutions with a shared
 370 vision for carrying out a study using FL; we refer to this collective as the *Working Group* (WG). An important prerequisite for the
 371 formation of a *Working Group* is that each individual institution identifies the key stakeholders who should be included in
 372 discussions and who have the authority to approve, use, or modify protocols that are necessary to make the study possible. These
 373 stakeholders can include principal investigators, research assistants, system administrators, research computing teams, IRB
 374 representatives, inter-organizational liaisons, clinicians, and other relevant technical or policy experts. While it may be tempting to
 375 build a large group of personnel right away, our recommendation is to keep the number of individuals to coordinate as low as
 376 possible by only including those who are absolutely necessary in initial conversations to ensure responsibilities and functional roles
 377 are clearly delegated and as a pragmatic concern to make it easier for the WG to meet. Taking a modular approach is advisable in
 378 building the components of a WG at each institution to improve communication efficiency; Figure 4 diagrams a possible way that
 379 one organization could establish functional modules for tackling intra-institutional challenges with the idea that these modules
 380 could operate with some autonomy and could have discussions about their respective tasks with equivalent modules at other
 381 institutions, while Figure 5 relates this modular structure to the functional roles at another hypothetical institution.

382

383 FIGURE 4: *A hypothetical organization of functional modules for an FL study at one institution. The various tasks that need to be*
 384 *managed by a WG can be assigned to individuals and sub-groups within each institution to focus communication and direct*
 385 *challenges to those who are equipped to address them.*

386

387 FIGURE 5: A theoretical mapping of responsibilities across roles at two collaborating institutions. In this example, it could be that
 388 Institution A is a research hospital that has an algorithm they are hoping will one day be useful in a clinical context and Institution
 389 B is an academic group with more experience in software development who will help them port the existing algorithm to a federated
 390 setting.

391

392 3.2.2. ESTABLISHING GOALS AND BUILDING RELATIONSHIPS

393 The first steps in forming a working group will require the initiating party to formulate their general vision for collaboration and
 394 find like-minded individuals or labs at other institutions. While an FL researcher may be drawn to a vision like “use Federated
 395 Learning to train a model for some task,” it can be difficult to secure buy-in from collaborators if the vision lacks domain specificity.
 396 A vision that is more likely to attract interest might be something like “use Federated Learning to train a model for classifying
 397 patients with Alzheimer’s Dementia based on fMRI scans,” or could even be specific to a particular technology and research
 398 question: “use Federated Learning to train our internally-validated virtual staining software for generating simulated Trichrome
 399 stains of liver cells from H&E whole slide images.” Articulating a vision that is too specific increases the risk that it may be hard
 400 to get commitments from external collaborators — what is in it for them to devote time and resources to help you validate your
 401 software or answer your question? The competitive nature of academic research and “publish or perish” atmosphere in some
 402 research contexts will make it difficult to secure interest of other groups unless incentive structures are well-aligned across

403 institutions. Relatedly, the vision should justify both the use of FL and the clinical importance of the applications; if the technology
404 that would be developed for the collaboration does not align with the needs of clinicians or could be better produced without FL,
405 it will be difficult to find eager collaborators and a poor use of resources. In the context of biomedical datasets, the curators of data
406 are often highly-trained and overworked — pathologists who annotate whole slide images used to train computer vision models,
407 for example — so ensuring these people are fairly compensated and invested in the project’s vision will be important to think about
408 early on.

409 Defining an appropriate vision for the project is closely tied into the challenges of securing buy-in from other groups, especially if
410 there do not exist relationships that can be leveraged to build mutual trust. The ideal scenario would be that researchers from the
411 collaborating institutions have already worked together on a similar project in the same domain, perhaps even a multicenter study
412 that required data pooling. In this case, it may be quite easy to coordinate an FL validation study with the goal of comparing results
413 obtained through FL to the gold-standard model trained on shared data, provided that stakeholders remain interested and have
414 enough sway; engineering the FL infrastructure is a straightforward bottleneck to pass through relative to the hurdles these
415 researchers would have already overcome in order to get approval for data sharing. At the other extreme of the trust spectrum would
416 be a WG formed by an eager initiator sending cold emails to labs with similar research interests. It is likely quite difficult to
417 successfully build coalitions this way and a reasonable middle-ground would seek to leverage existing connections by looking for
418 a researcher whose affiliation may have changed, who has cross-institutional mentorship relationships, or who has attended mutual
419 conferences. Detailed suggestions for networking are out of scope for the current work, but we direct the reader to a previous paper
420 describing the formation of a multicenter clinical trial which includes a discussion of methods for building consensus that can be
421 used to overcome barriers in trust and goal alignment when forming a WG that does not have extensive existing relationships⁵⁴.
422 Building from a shared vision to shared values and then narrowing to a more specific mission statement and laying out the path to
423 achieve this mission is another strategy for developing engagement that other research consortiums have utilized⁵⁵.

424 With a guiding vision and basic trust within the WG, the specific goals of the collaboration can be discussed. This can include the
425 expectations in terms of individual contributions and length of the commitment, the target type of publication(s) or presentation(s),
426 and a research question with a plan for how it can be evaluated. A useful mnemonic of criteria for a research question, also adapted
427 by ⁵⁴ is FINER: Feasible, Interesting, Novel, Ethical, Relevant⁵⁶. Considering clinical alignment and consulting clinicians or
428 patients in early development is valuable to understand if there is utility in the proposed study and to mitigate potentials for
429 algorithmic and experimental bias or inequitable distribution of benefits^{4,7,57,58}. These shared expectations do not have to be rigid
430 and it is likely that they will be adjusted over the *Planning Stage* as nuances of implementation impact the type of work that is
431 feasible, however, ensuring that all participants are in agreement regarding what they want to get out of the collaboration will be
432 essential for success. It is also worth noting that establishing metrics for evaluating the success of the *Working Group* in terms of
433 its efficiency of communication and efficacy at overcoming the challenges to FL collaborations we have laid out would be desirable
434 so this information can be codified and lower the barrier to entry for future multicenter FL studies. Another useful acronym for
435 determining objectives of the collaboration is SMART: Specific, Measurable, Achievable/Attainable, Relevant/Realistic, and
436 Time-bound^{59,60}. Keeping these criteria in mind while establishing goals will help to solidify shared ideals and ensure that the
437 collaboration is well-motivated.

438 3.2.3. ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL READINESS

439 Also within the *Preplanning Stage* and closely related to the formation of a WG is the initiation of an *Assessment of (Intra- or*
440 *Inter-) Institutional Readiness* (AIR), though it will be possible to treat the AIR as a step in the process of refining the approach

441 that will be developed in the *Planning Stage* and thus may be carried out multiple times with a varying emphasis and scope across
442 the *Preplanning* and *Planning* phases. The AIR should be suited to the specific research context and site, but the primary themes
443 we have identified can be categorized as follows: Members, Objectives, Technology, Obstacles, Resources (MOTOR, “use a
444 MOTOR to get in the AIR”). The MOTOR framework is depicted in Figure 6, and detailed descriptions of these themes and
445 example questions to consider when building out a MOTOR checklist can be found in Supplementary Table 2.

446

447

448 FIGURE 6: *The MOTOR framework for carrying out an Assessment of Institutional Readiness.*

449 While the AIR-MOTOR approach should first be applied at the scope of each institution in the collaboration, its value will be
450 maximized by building a shared repository of tangible findings across institutions (e.g., checklists stored with version-control
451 software). Doing so can help to build rapport and transparency, identify gaps in the spirit of open science and peer-review, and
452 maintain investment by demonstrating commitment and progress towards the *Working Group's* shared vision. Where it is possible
453 to do so without exposing sensitive information, these checklists could be open-sourced as part of the project's publication to
454 provide concrete examples for future collaborations to draw from. We can think of the AIR as two related tools, an Assessment of
455 Intra-Institutional Readiness and a subsequent Assessment of Inter-Institutional Readiness, but refer to these under the same
456 umbrella term as the scope of the system under evaluation by each AIR implementation will vary as the collaboration develops.
457 Aggregating and synthesizing the AIRs of each stakeholder through iterative refinement will help bridge the gap between the
458 *Preplanning Stage* and the *Planning Stage*. For example, sharing objectives and goals will ensure that incentive structures are
459 aligned across institutions and assessments of technical readiness are an important part of algorithmic fine-tuning that will start to
460 take place well before the final training and testing in the *Execution and Evaluation Stage*.

461 3.3. STEP 2: THE PLANNING STAGE

462 After the WG has established communication procedures, settled on a guiding scope and vision for their collaboration, and
463 initialized a shared repository for their inaugural AIRs, they are equipped to advance into the core *Planning Stage* where they will
464 flesh out the logistical and technical strategies that will enable the project to move forward. The types of considerations relevant at
465 this point are depicted in Figure 7.

466

467

468
469 FIGURE 7: The four core components of the Planning Stage: Financing, Data Governance, Ethics and Approvals, and
470 Computational Infrastructure.

471 3.3.1. 2A: FINANCING

472 After the formation of an initial *Working Group* has laid the groundwork for a multicenter study, one of the issues that will need to
473 be addressed early on in order for work to progress is where the funding for the project will come from. There are several potential
474 avenues that can be pursued depending on the type of collaboration and the institutions involved, but three major paradigms are as
475 follows: (1) one or more institutions with funding and a vested interest in seeing the project to completion sponsor the other partners,
476 (2) each institution is expected to fund themselves, or (3) the institutions write a joint grant proposal.

477 The first scenario is most applicable to cases in which the initiating institution is looking to validate a technology they have
478 developed for a broader population, in which case they may be willing to put up the funding required and loan or grant computing
479 hardware to their collaborators in exchange for their help in validation, and the collaborators may be more inclined to contribute to
480 the project if they don't have to worry about financing it themselves and the technology seems like a good opportunity to submit a
481 manuscript for publication — perhaps one that could be referenced in future grant proposals relating to the development of and/or
482 applications in multicenter FL.

483 Likely the most accessible of the three paradigms is the second, as it distributes the burden of financing across institutions and
484 could be funded from existing grants that cover exploration of related technologies or research questions. Targeting intramural
485 funding mechanisms may be appropriate here, especially as these grants are typically easier to obtain than those from national
486 funding sources. Internal funding may also increase the awareness and responsiveness of institutional leadership to the FL effort
487 and can also serve as a precursor to procuring external funding with collaborating institutions. If the collaborating institutions have
488 their own computing infrastructure already that is sufficient for the task at hand, it could be the case that not much funding is needed
489 to obtain the human resources required to enable the study, though this is also dependent on the data and personnel available due
490 to the high cost of protected time for researchers and physicians. In cases where this funding approach is viable, it is advisable that
491 the WG maintain clear records of which individuals and what tasks are funded by each funding source to prevent confusion in
492 cashflow from causing problems as the project matures and money is spent.

493 The third paradigm is likely the ideal for FL collaborations to aspire to, but the existing avenues for explicitly pursuing a joint grant
494 based on FL are limited. One possibility is the NIH Clinical Trial Planning Grant Program R34 mechanism, which can be used to
495 cover expenses in the *Preplanning* and *Planning* stages as we describe them here, and has previously been used to fund the
496 development of multicenter controlled clinical trials (MCCTs)^{54,61}. The NIH R01 mechanism can be used to fund the execution
497 phase of MCCTs, but may not explicitly apply to FL projects. However, the absence of explicit R01 request for proposals (RFPs)

498 does not prevent submission of an investigator initiated R01 (cap is \$500k, and as much as \$750k with pre-approval) with Federated
499 Learning taking front and center. Depending on the project goals and funding needs, the R03 small grant mechanism or the R21
500 exploratory/developmental grant mechanism could be options to pursue, but the short history of FL as a methodology and lack of
501 general familiarity with it in bioinformatics may make it difficult to persuade reviewers. Other grants that have contributed to
502 funding multicenter FL projects in healthcare include: 1) the NIH NCI F30 Dual Degree Fellowship, 2) the NHI P50 Specialized
503 Center Grant⁶², 3) the NIH DP5 grant^{63,64}, 4) the NIH U01 and U24 grants, 5) the NIH NIBIB training grant, and 6) an NSF IIS
504 grant⁶⁵. Typically, F grants and training grants offer stipend support which can fund investigator involvement in such collaborations.
505 There is also potential for federated collaborations to form an Administrative Core supported by an NIH NIGMS Center of
506 Biomedical Research Excellence (COBRE) grant – the goal of this set of grant mechanisms is to build multidisciplinary research
507 infrastructure united by a common theme through establishment of Administrative Cores and to support advancement of junior
508 investigators by providing them with funding to serve as leaders on Pilot or Research Projects and connecting them to mentors in
509 institutional leadership. COBRE grants are awarded to states which acquire disproportionately less NIH funding and thus may be
510 highly applicable for fostering collaboration across smaller biomedical institutions, especially in rural areas⁶⁶. Collaboration
511 amongst COBREs is highly encouraged.

512 Another factor that may influence the way funding is obtained or distributed across institutions is in the potential benefits of the
513 work. For example, the institution that expects to have the first author or to decide what publications to target may face more
514 pressure to contribute funding to the other participants. If there is potential for the product of the work to be monetized, this will
515 further complicate the responsibilities for funding, but may be worked out in the form of a subcontract. It is best that appropriate
516 agreements are reached to address distribution of benefits before funding is obtained to ensure researchers will not feel they have
517 been deceived down the road – establishing contracts in early discussions or implementing procedures for automated effort tracking
518 are potential options to consider here.

519 3.3.2. 2B: DATA GOVERNANCE

520 One of the major logistical challenges that multicenter FL studies face is the development of appropriate data governance
521 strategies⁶². There are quite a wide range of considerations that go into a good data governance plan, and approaches for formalizing
522 practices vary substantially within the literature, but we have identified the following four core themes: data definitions,
523 accountability and stewardship, privacy, and security. These themes are depicted in Figure 8 below and are discussed with more
524 details and example questions in Supplementary Table 3. A comprehensive data governance plan which appropriately covers these
525 themes will incorporate the following concepts as they are applicable: rules of engagement, purpose of use, data definitions, metrics
526 of success, decision rights, ethics, accountabilities, controls, organizational bodies, stakeholders, data governance officers, data
527 stewards, proactive and reactive processes, collation, standardization, harmonization, privacy, security, retention, audits, training,
528 approval for use, anonymization/deidentification, storage, quality metrics and assurances, and transfer policies, among others<sup>52,67–
529 74</sup>. These issues are all closely interconnected and will necessarily tie into other steps of our proposal. For example, the *Working*
530 *Group* should start thinking about differences in their data representations during their early AIRs in the *Preplanning Stage* as they
531 relate their data resources, technological needs, and the research question; they will now start to outline the roles, policies, and
532 processes that can be leveraged to manage semantic harmonization of their records; and in the *Execution and Evaluation Stage* they
533 will need to actually engineer the data preprocessing pipeline and ensure that inputs are in the expected format across institutions.

534

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540 FIGURE 8: Core data governance concepts/themes relevant to multicenter FL.

541 3.3.3. 2C: ETHICS AND APPROVALS

542 The formalization of a data governance plan will be critical for ensuring the ethical justification and approval for the study. The
 543 data governance plan will provide assurance that data will be utilized only in accordance with laid out rules and procedures and
 544 can regulate what types of data will be shared between institutions. In a recent multicenter study of prostate cancer using federated
 545 training of DL models for classifying MRI imaging, the data sharing agreements specified that only model weights would be
 546 transferred, and no private data would be exchanged⁶². Agreements of this type should be highly desirable in order for FL to deliver
 547 on its potential benefits, but it may not always be possible to operate under such strong assumptions about the privacy of model
 548 sharing. As we introduced previously, attacks on data privacy can be used to expose sensitive information from model parameters
 549 — the potential harm that would be caused by such a violation may justify extra precautions in cases where the data belong to small
 550 or vulnerable populations that are more readily identifiable. Sharing model parameters cannot pose a more significant threat to
 551 privacy than sharing data does, as the information contained in the data would be sufficient to produce the information contained
 552 in the model parameters under the right circumstances, but not vice versa. If the project is valuable enough that a study of pooled
 553 data could be justified, then FL should be an acceptable replacement that could only decrease the risk to patient privacy.

554 The operating assumptions for seeking ethical approval may also depend on the IRB’s understanding of FL and Machine Learning
 555 more broadly. If the IRB members do not have a clear conceptual model for what the weights and biases of a neural net are, it
 556 would be unfair to expect them to know what FL entails, how it leaks information, and the extent to which this leakage threatens
 557 data privacy. To this end, IRB education efforts are valuable endeavors to improve understanding of the benefits of FL and ensure
 558 that its benefits and risks are represented fairly. Regardless of the assumptions made regarding FL information leakage, informed
 559 patient consent or waivers of consent where applicable will need to be obtained during this step of the *Planning Stage*. Differing
 560 patient consent forms across institutions can regulate the types of applications permissible for each dataset — for example, if one
 561 institution has consent forms that permit commercialization of patient data and others do not. Implementing HIPAA-compliant

562 logging of data access in case of a patient-requested audit may be necessary in this stage, dependent on the level of consent required
563 to carry out the study.

564 3.3.4. 2D: COMPUTATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE

565 The remaining segment of the *Planning Stage* involves building and coordinating the computational infrastructure required for
566 collaborative model training. This includes engineering the FL framework or adapting the technology under consideration to train
567 in a distributed fashion and to work with each institution’s resources, finding secure protocols for authenticating users and
568 communicating model updates between participants and the aggregation server, and validating the integrity of the approach to
569 ensure only approved information is shared.

570 Depending on the context and goals of the project, engineering the FL codebase may be a comparatively simple task in the
571 development of computational infrastructure. For example, if the multicenter collaboration aims to evaluate a particular technology
572 which has already been designed with FL in mind or which is implemented using tools that work well across computing platforms,
573 such as Singularity containers^{75,76} with CUDA^{77,78} compatibility, it would be a straightforward process to ensure that the technology
574 works across institutions without idiosyncrasies. In addition to containerization, continuous integration and analysis can be
575 employed to reduce problems posed by heterogeneity of computing environments and to promote reproducibility of results^{79,80}. In
576 collaborations where the primary motivation is to study a particular domain, disease, or health-related research question, the
577 development of an *ad hoc* software for the study would be a major engineering task to carry out in this step of the *Planning Phase*
578 whereas software broadly applicable across multiple subspecialties may be more flexible.

579 The second category of issues are closely related to the issues of data security and privacy discussed in section 2b, but have a wider
580 reach than just the training data. System administrators or other IT personnel with authority to manage incoming and outgoing
581 connections should already be familiar with the WG, but will now have an essential role in modifying firewalls selectively to allow
582 collaborating institutions to connect with the aggregation server. Determining where these server(s) will be hosted — for example,
583 on a third-party cloud computing platform (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud) or by one or more of the participants — is another task that
584 falls under this category. We previously claimed that the privacy risk of sharing model updates is no greater than the risk of sharing
585 data directly, but this is only true when the methods used to transfer model updates are secure. If updates are not encrypted for
586 communication or the protocol that links any institution to the server can be manipulated by a malicious third party, it would be
587 possible for external attackers not included in the assumptions of the model sharing agreement to access sensitive information in
588 transit. It is also worth noting at this point that existing security protocols within institutions can be leveraged to protect the training
589 environment without requiring an entirely new set of operating procedures — a recurring motif in the benefits that FL can offer
590 when applied efficiently⁹. User authentication is a good use-case for this strategy (though not perfect as DOS attacks remain a
591 concern) since we can expect most research institutions that hold sensitive patient data to have systems for authenticating users and
592 managing their permissions, which can be used to create accounts for collaborating researchers with access limited to the strictly-
593 necessary networking protocols.

594 Lastly, successfully addressing the challenges pertaining to computational infrastructure will also require that the WG can validate
595 the integrity of the code that will be executed and prove to system administrators and ethics overseers that the information will only
596 be communicated in the way it has been described. Leveraging technologies such as trusted execution environments, linting (i.e.,
597 using automated tools to check for common code errors) paired with unit tests and integration tests, containerization, and formal
598 verification can aid in this process, but this is a difficult problem and detailed discussion is outside the scope of this paper. Managing
599 skill match and training across sites is a fundamental part of overcoming these obstacles because each institution must have

600 personnel who understand the technology sufficiently to explain how it works and check that it is mechanistically sound. If the
 601 technology was developed by one institution, they will be responsible for code walkthroughs, workshops, or other instructional
 602 endeavors to catch their collaborators up to speed. Even if the technology is developed as a collective effort, producing a plan for
 603 what to do when things go wrong and educating all participants about their responsibilities in execution and best practices for
 604 approaching technical problems will be necessary for keeping the FL system infrastructure robust, reinforcing weak spots, and
 605 eliminating single points of failure.

606 3.4. STEP 3: THE EXECUTION AND EVALUATION STAGE

607 When the obstacles identified by each institution in their AIRs have been addressed and the core themes of the *Planning Stage* are
 608 understood by the WG with confidence, the collaboration is ready to move into the final stage of our proposal depicted in Figure
 609 9: *Execution and Evaluation*.

610
 611 FIGURE 9: *The five components of the Execution and Evaluation Stage: The Dry Run, Finalization of Experimental Settings,*
 612 *Training and Testing, Formalizations and Sharing Knowledge, and Maintaining Relationships.*

613 3.4.1. 3A: THE DRY RUN

614 While the execution of a dry run is not yet viewed as a necessary step in the best practices of multicenter studies, we include it in
 615 our framework on the basis that it is an extremely valuable tool to serve as a final Assessment of Inter-Institutional Readiness. At
 616 the minimum, a synthesis of the previous Assessments of Intra-Institutional Readiness and the steps that have been taken to address
 617 the obstacles identified should be carried out with input from all collaborators to ensure nothing has slipped through the cracks.
 618 Better than this synthesis, but not mutually exclusive from it, would be to carry out a dry run of the study in question. This could
 619 be done using publicly available datasets in a similar domain to that of the task in question, partitioning them among participants,
 620 and carrying out the study as if it were truly private data. There is likely no better tool to find bugs — whether they be in the code
 621 or in the communication and governance procedures — than simulating the real experiment as it would be carried out. A perfect
 622 dry run would be a mark of a well thought-out collaboration and a dry run that does see unexpected errors arise gives the participants
 623 a chance to make adjustments and fix problems that might not have been caught without seeing all the moving parts operating

624 together, without risking the consequences of failure on a truly private dataset. The dry run is also a useful assessment of prior
625 training efforts carried out in the *Planning Stage* to educate participants about their responsibilities and how to use the technology
626 during training and testing; it is one thing to explain how a system works and another thing to actually use the system. Stress testing
627 and attempting to intentionally force system errors are another optional component that could be included here.

628 3.4.2. 3B: FINALIZATION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

629 Although the experimental setup should be largely determined by the time a WG is ready for their dry run, lessons learned from
630 practice execution may inform the final settings that will be used. Some of the variables that need to be considered here and have
631 not already been explicitly discussed include the model architecture, the optimizer and scheduler, the loss function and evaluation
632 metrics, the hyperparameters, whether seeds for reproducibility will be used, the training/validation/testing dataset split (e.g.,
633 partitioning of nested observations within patient into different sets without introducing unmeasured confounding and procedures
634 for class balancing), the aggregation function, the method for selecting participants to train in each iteration, the number of iterations
635 and frequency of updates, the criteria for selecting the best model or stopping the training process, and any other settings specific
636 to the context and application in question (e.g., if differential noise is added to updates, what is the privacy budget?⁴⁸). Some of
637 these settings may also vary and it is possible for the collaboration to spend time optimizing hyper- or meta-parameters, but a plan
638 to do so should be agreed upon in advance to maintain shared expectations among participants. It is even okay to “play it by ear”
639 when picking hyperparameters for different runs, but this strategy should be chosen before training begins so everyone knows what
640 they are signing up for and no one is expected to take up computational resources on trials they did not expect or want to participate
641 in. One aspect of the experimental setup that may not have been considered thus far is whether it is appropriate to include stopping
642 criteria to mitigate the risk of biased inference — this could include evaluation of model interpretation and reliability to ensure the
643 gradient updates and predictions across participants are similar and explainable.

644 3.4.3. 3C: TRAINING AND TESTING

645 If the steps we have described thus far have been carried out successfully, the process of training and testing the model should be
646 quite straightforward. The training process is carried out iteratively as described in the background section, utilizing the
647 infrastructure developed in 2d, and following the procedure finalized in 3b. Implementing periodic “sanity checks” (e.g., manually
648 checking model predictions for a few instances to ensure they are reasonable) can be useful to limit unexpected problems in
649 evaluation. Steps for model evaluation should also have been articulated by this point, but these can go beyond just accuracy metrics
650 — this is an opportunity to take advantage of the combined expertise and unique data of multiple institutions. If it has been
651 determined that sharing summary statistics regarding the patient cohorts of each institution is acceptable, the investigators could
652 set out to determine which types of patients the model works best for and which types of data it fails to account for. Furthermore,
653 clinicians or outside experts at each institution could be consulted to help the collaborators better understand the possible use-cases
654 for their model, as well as drawbacks and blind spots they may have missed thus far. This also relates to the next step in the
655 *Execution and Evaluation Stage*, which aims to expand the assessment and interpretation of the project beyond its model
656 performance to the success of the collaboration as a whole.

657 3.4.4. 3D: FORMALIZING AND SHARING KNOWLEDGE

658 Our goal in this paper is to provide a roadmap that will facilitate the formation of *Working Groups* of small institutions seeking to
659 utilize FL to train models for digital healthcare applications; we hope our proposal will be useful to researchers seeking to navigate
660 the obstacles we have discussed, but it is no substitute for practical experience. WGs that share our vision and see the great

661 advantages FL can bring to personalized medicine will play a critical role in the advancement of the field by codifying their take-
662 aways from successful (or unsuccessful) collaborations and sharing these openly to the benefit of us all. The communication of
663 such knowledge should not focus just on the technical considerations and consist of loss curves or confusion matrices but needs to
664 include details of the logistical concerns like data governance protocols and methods for maintaining stakeholder investment.
665 Although it may be difficult to incentivize groups to report failures or null findings, we emphasize that the formation of federated
666 coalition is a success to be celebrated even when optimal models are not developed. It would be beneficial to all FL researchers for
667 WGs to establish additional performance metrics that pertain to the success of the collaboration and not just the model – an
668 implementation scientist could be included in the WG to aid in the development of these metrics (see ⁸¹). An example of what this
669 could look like comes from the recently formed Cardiovascular Quality Improvement and Care Innovation Consortium, which
670 identified reach, effectiveness, adoption, implementation, and maintenance as measures they wanted to emphasize in evaluating
671 their multicenter care improvement projects⁵⁵. These metrics and the SMART goals determined in the *Preplanning Stage* provide
672 a good starting point, but the standard practices for evaluating FL collaborations are likely to evolve over time as more real-world
673 work is done to identify useful approaches to formalize their strengths and weaknesses.

674 3.4.5. 3E: MAINTAINING RELATIONSHIPS AND LOOKING FORWARD

675 The last step we propose in the *Execution and Evaluation Stage* seeks to provide a way forward for future collaborations. While
676 the sharing of knowledge we advocate for in 3d will lower the barrier to entry for other groups, the greatest advantage that any
677 collaboration offers is to its participants. With the trust and rapport that come from working together, as well as the shared
678 understanding of policies or procedures that worked and those that did not, the institutions that make it this far in our proposed
679 framework would have a much easier time coordinating an additional multicenter study, MCCTs, or an extension of the project in
680 question. Previous components of our framework can be iterated through as necessary to refine the technology or the contribution
681 this project makes to the existing body of knowledge and methods. Even if not every participant is interested in continuing research
682 in this area, it is valuable to maintain connections to facilitate easier collaborations as opportunities arise in the future.
683 Demonstrating an interest in FL applications for healthcare and experience navigating the obstacles that must be traversed for these
684 studies is likely to get attention from other potential collaborators, and showing a commitment to maintaining relationships within
685 the growing community of small institutions involved in this research will encourage others to do the same and help to expand the
686 network within this space.

687 Moving forward from a successful collaboration also requires the participants to think about what should be done with their model
688 in accordance with their underlying motivations for its development. As an example, commercialization of the end product may
689 complicate relations amongst collaborators if expectations are not addressed prior to initiating a collaboration. Following the
690 production of a useful high-performance model with clinical relevance, there should be a conversation about what else needs to be
691 done to get this tool into the hands of clinicians. This will present additional logistical challenges and will often require further
692 validation studies, but opening a dialogue within the WG will promote continued stakeholder involvement and ownership over
693 their efforts while allowing the collective expertise of participants to guide the next steps. The algorithms that can be formed out
694 of multicenter FL have great promise for use by small institutions that could not produce the same results on their own, so a core
695 priority in wrapping up this component of the project is to build an understanding of how this promise can be turned into a reality.

696 4. CONCLUSION

697 The age of precision medicine is upon us, but applications of machine learning in healthcare face significant problems with
698 generalizability because a very limited subset of the population is represented in the datasets for these models^{6,7,9}. Many of the
699 people left out of the potential benefits of ML-assisted medicine are served by smaller health systems or institutions based in rural
700 areas and other under resourced contexts (e.g., global health), which have been deeply affected by an emerging crisis in healthcare
701 accessibility that has become increasingly visible throughout the Covid-19 pandemic^{4,51,57,58,82-85}. Federated Learning offers these
702 institutions a way to train models collaboratively without exposing private patient data, and has the potential to empower small
703 research groups in a way that has previously not been possible⁹. There are quite a few technical, theoretical, and logistical challenges
704 that must be addressed in order for these collaborations to become a reality, but the existing literature has devoted little attention
705 to such pragmatic concerns. We seek to fill this gap in knowledge by evaluating some of the obstacles small research groups face
706 in implementing multicenter FL and proposing a framework for them to effectively overcome these obstacles. We are hopeful that
707 this contribution will provide a useful guide for the formation of *Working Groups* focused on FL applications in healthcare where
708 there previously was none and are optimistic about the role small institutions will play in the future of digital medicine.

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